

Modeling of mutagenicity of aromatic and heteroaromatic amines in *Salmonella typhimurium* TA98 : Role of hydrophobicity and topological indices

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Abstract : Topological modeling of mutagenicity of 88 aromatic and heteroaromatic amines acting on *Salmonella typhimurium* is reported using distance-based and connectivity indices including Balaban and Balaban type indices. The dependence of mutagenic activity is investigated under three different headings : (i) using topological indices alone; (ii) using log P in combination with the topological indices and (iii) using Balaban and Balaban type indices alone. The results have shown that though more or less similar results are obtained in all the three categories, the involvement of log P term gave slightly better results. Furthermore the results show that the mutagenic activity is a function of size of the aromatic ring system. The results are discussed critically using a variety of statistical parameters.

Keywords : Mutagenicity, QSAR, topological index, Balaban type indices, heteroaromatic amine, hydrophobicity, aromatic amine.

Introduction

In an earlier communication¹ it was argued that understanding and predicting the chronic toxic effects of chemicals, especially carcinogenicity has become one of the major problem facing chemists involved with the development of industrial chemicals such as pesticides, drugs etc.; as well as scientist studying the toxicology of natural products. In yet another publication² it was advocated that over the years chemists have been impressed by the great importance of hydrophobic effects in chemical-biological interactions as brought out by quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR). It seems timely to examine those instances where hydrophobic terms are not significant. All such approaches were non-topological in nature i.e. molecular descriptors other than topological indices were used in such investigations. In particular, earlier we have used hydrophobic parameters. The Indian group, under the leadership of Khadikar reinvestigated such cases using distance-based connectivity topological indices and observed that better results are obtained even without using log P term³⁻¹². In con-

tinuation to these results the present communication deals with topological modeling of mutagenicity (log TA98) of 88 aromatic and heteroaromatic amines in *Salmonella typhimurium* TA98 in that we have used a series of distance-based and connectivity topological indices including Balaban and Balaban type indices¹³ and is the extension of our earlier report¹². In an earlier study we have used the first 88 compounds from Table 1 and modeled their mutagenic activity using log P, E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} and an indicator parameter IL related to the size of the aromatic ring system as the correlating parameter. The earlier results obtained by us¹² are summarized below :

Model	Parameters used	n	r	S	F
1	log P	88	0.723	1.329	94.1
2	IL	88	0.771	1.224	126.0
3	log P, IL	88	0.875	0.938	61.6
4	log P, IL, E_{HOMO}	88	0.882	0.918	4.7
5	log P, IL, E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO}	88	0.898	0.860	12.6

Our earlier study¹² indicated that log TA98 is a linear

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Table 1. Parent structures used in the present study

function of both log P and IL. However, there we have not used any topological index for modeling the activity. In the present study we aim to use distance-based as well as connectivity topological indices¹⁴⁻¹⁹ for modeling mutagenic activities of aromatic and heteroaromatic amines whose parent structures are presented in Table 1 while the set of 88 amines used are listed in Table 2. The Table 3 recorded the list of molecular descriptors used in modeling log TA98. The mutagenic activity (log TA98), log P, E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} indices along with the values of indicator parameter IL are presented in Table 2. The connectivity indices are shown in Table 3, Balaban and Balaban type indices are given in Table 4. Correlations of the molecular descriptors used and their correlation with log TA98 and log P are presented in Table 5.

The aim of current study is three fold : (i) modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) using topological indices alone i.e. without the use of log P; (ii) modeling of the mutagenic activity (log TA98) by combining log P with the topological indices and (iii) modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) using Balaban type indices¹⁹ along. Further, we will first examine the entire set of 95 compounds and then will model the mutagenic activity of 88 compounds, used in our earlier study¹² for compari-

son. To meet these goals, we will carry out 2D QSAR modeling using maximum- R^2 method²⁰. The result as discussed below, suggest that topological indices are powerful tool for modeling the mutagenic activity. The mutagenic activity was adopted from our earlier study. It is worth mentioning that the topological indices were calculated using the DRAGON software²¹ and the structure optimization was done using Hyperchem²² ACD Lab software²³. The statistically significant regression parameter and quality of correlation are show in Table 6.

(i) Modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) with topological indices and without using log P :

For the entire set of 95 compounds the best model was obtained with a combination of four parameters, out of which three are topological indices (W , ${}^1\chi$, Jhetv) and the fourth one is the indicator parameter IL. Using this combination the following results are obtained :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & -10.276 - 0.005 (\pm 0.002) W \\ & + 1.308 (\pm 0.280) {}^1\chi + 1.01 (\pm 0.410) \text{Jhetv} \\ & + 1.865 (\pm 0.330) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$n = 95, \text{Se} = 1.071, R = 0.839, R^2_A = 0.690, F = 53\,429, Q = 0.783$$

Here, and here after n is the number of compounds; Se is the standard error of estimation, R is the multiple correlation coefficient, R^2_A is the adjusted R^2 . F is the Fishers statistics and Q is the Pogliani quality factor²⁴⁻²⁶. In the above model [eq. (1)] ${}^1\chi$ is the first-order Randic connectivity¹⁵ whose positive coefficient suggests that the number of atoms and first-order branching is favorable for the exhibition of the mutagenic activity (log TA98). Like ${}^1\chi$, the coefficient of Jhetv¹⁹ is also positive. This indicates that van der Waals weighted distance is favorable for the exhibition of the activity. The negative coefficient of W ¹⁴ in the above model [eq. (1)] is probably due to its high co-linearity with ${}^1\chi$ index.

Since in our earlier study¹² we have used the first 88 compounds out of the entire set of 95 compounds, we have further carried out modeling using these 88 compounds. Here, the best 2D QSAR model was obtained with five topological indices (J , Jhetv, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^2\chi^v$, ${}^2\Delta$) and an indicator parameter IL. This model was found as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & -7.243 - 1.089 (\pm 0.639) J \\ & + 1.876 (\pm 0.427) \text{Jhetv} + 2.584 (\pm 0.739) {}^2\chi \\ & - 2.001 (\pm 0.745) {}^2\chi^v - 1.904 (\pm 0.705) {}^2\Delta \\ & + 2.364 (\pm 0.270) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.967, R = 0.873, R^2_A = 0.744, F = 43.168, Q = 0.903$$

Table 2. Name of the compounds, mutagenicity, indicator parameter and quantum chemical descriptors used in the present study

Compd. no.	Compds.	log TA98	log P	E _{LUMO}	E _{HOMO}	IL
1.	2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene	2.62	3.92	-0.405	-8.236	1
2.	2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline (<i>p</i> -cresidine)	-2.05	1.74	0.419	-8.449	0
3.	5-Aminoquinoline	-2.00	1.16	-0.395	-8.395	0
4.	4-Ethoxyaniline (<i>p</i> -phenetidine)	-2.30	1.24	0.513	-8.182	0
5.	1-Aminonaphthalene	-0.60	2.25	-0.195	-8.108	0
6.	4-Aminofluorene	1.13	2.70	-0.157	-8.256	1
7.	2-Aminoanthracene	2.62	3.26	-0.771	-7.869	1
8.	7-Aminofluoranthene	2.88	3.72	-0.895	-8.186	1
9.	8-Aminoquinoline	-1.14	1.79	-0.294	-8.134	0
10.	1,7-Diaminophenazine	0.75	1.64	-1.045	-8.089	1
11.	2-Aminonaphthalene	-0.67	2.28	-0.198	-8.227	0
12.	4-Aminopyrene	3.16	3.72	-0.850	-7.837	1
13.	3-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.55	2.68	-1.034	-8.801	0
14.	2,4,5-Trimethylaniline	-1.32	2.41	0.581	-8.244	0
15.	3-Aminofluorene	0.89	2.70	-0.182	-8.333	1
16.	3,3'-Dichlorobenzidine	0.81	3.51	-0.142	-8.125	0
17.	2,4-Dimethylaniline (2,4-xylydine)	-2.22	1.68	0.605	-8.288	0
18.	2,7-Diaminofluorene	0.48	1.47	0.000	-7.753	1
19.	3-Aminofluoranthene	3.31	4.20	-0.818	-8.033	1
20.	2-Aminofluorene	1.93	3.14	-0.108	-8.106	1
21.	2-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.62	2.68	-1.148	-8.852	0
22.	4-Aminobiphenyl	-0.14	2.86	0.048	-8.263	0
23.	3-Methoxy-4-methylaniline (<i>o</i> -cresidine)	-1.96	1.52	0.583	-8.274	0
24.	2-Aminocarbazole	0.60	2.30	0.025	-8.023	1
25.	2-Amino-5-nitrophenol	-2.52	1.36	-0.923	-9.052	0
26.	2,2'-Diaminobiphenyl	-1.52	1.58	0.267	-8.193	0
27.	2-Hydroxy-7-aminofluorene	0.41	2.03	-0.127	-7.998	1
28.	1-Aminophenanthrene	2.38	3.26	-0.357	-8.132	1
29.	2,5-Dimethylaniline (2,5-xylydine)	-2.40	1.83	0.581	-8.404	0
30.	4-Amino-2'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.92	2.68	-0.554	-8.597	0
31.	2-Amino-4-methylphenol	-2.10	1.16	0.478	-8.274	0
32.	2-Aminophenazine	0.55	2.18	-1.165	-8.495	1
33.	4-Aminophenylsulfide	0.31	2.18	0.047	-7.528	0
34.	2,4-Dinitroaniline	-2.00	1.84	-1.491	-9.931	0
35.	2,4-Diaminoisopropylbenzene	-3.00	1.12	0.722	-8.121	0
36.	2,4-Difluoroaniline	-2.70	1.54	-0.085	-8.695	0
37.	4,4'-Methylenedianiline	-1.60	1.59	0.576	-8.274	0
38.	3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine	0.01	2.34	0.185	-7.873	0
39.	2-Aminofluoranthene	3.23	3.72	-0.887	-8.273	1
40.	2-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.89	2.68	-1.029	-8.746	0
41.	1-Aminofluoranthene	3.35	3.72	-0.816	-8.159	1
42.	4,4'-Ethylenebis(aniline)	-2.15	2.13	0.589	-8.318	0
43.	4-Chloroaniline	-2.52	1.88	0.284	-8.568	0
44.	2-Aminophenanthrene	2.46	3.26	-0.365	-8.233	1
45.	4-Fluoroaniline	-3.32	1.15	0.275	-8.560	0
46.	9-Aminophenanthrene	2.98	3.56	-0.364	-8.099	1
47.	3,3'-Diaminobiphenyl	-1.30	1.58	0.056	-8.414	0
48.	2-Aminopyrene	3.50	3.72	-0.865	-8.144	1
49.	2,6-Dichloro-1,4-phenylenediamine	-0.69	1.79	-0.029	-8.180	0
50.	2-Amino-7-acetamidofluorene	1.18	1.72	-0.143	-7.876	1
51.	2,8-Diaminophenazine	1.12	1.64	-1.039	-8.369	1
52.	6-Aminoquinoline	-2.67	1.28	-0.383	-8.443	0
53.	4-Methoxy-2-methylaniline (<i>m</i> -cresidine)	-3.00	1.23	0.474	-8.152	0
54.	3-Amino-2'-nitrophenyl	-1.30	2.68	-0.648	-8.665	0
55.	2,4'-Diaminobiphenyl	-0.92	1.58	0.215	-8.144	0
56.	1,6-Diaminophenazine	0.20	1.64	-1.058	-7.967	1

Table-2 (contd.)

57.	4-Aminophenyldisulfide	-1.03	1.99	-1.330	-8.209	0
58.	2-Bromo-4,6-dinitroaniline	-0.54	2.78	-1.691	-10.018	0
59.	2,4-Diamino- <i>n</i> -butylbenzene	-2.70	1.77	0.702	-8.130	0
60.	4-Aminophenylether	-1.14	1.36	0.317	-8.167	0
61.	2-Aminobiphenyl	-1.49	2.84	0.107	-8.407	0
62.	1,9-Diaminophenazine	0.04	1.64	-1.040	-7.997	1
63.	1-Aminofluorene	0.43	3.18	-0.191	-8.467	1
64.	8-Aminofluoranthene	3.80	3.72	-0.853	-8.166	1
65.	2-Chloroaniline	-3.00	1.90	0.268	-8.632	0
66.	3-Amino- <i>aaa</i> -trifluorotoluene	-0.80	2.29	-0.104	-9.032	0
67.	2-Amino-1-nitronaphthalene	-1.17	2.95	-0.998	-8.800	0
68.	3-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	0.69	2.68	-1.178	-8.879	0
69.	4-Bromoaniline	-2.70	2.26	0.212	-8.620	0
70.	2-Amino-4-chlorophenol	-3.00	1.81	0.154	-8.508	0
71.	3,3'-Dimethoxybenzidine	0.15	1.81	-0.005	-7.927	0
72.	4-Cyclohexylaniline	-1.24	3.65	0.620	-8.380	0
73.	4-Phenoxyaniline	0.38	2.96	0.255	-8.598	0
74.	4,4'-Methylenebis (<i>o</i> -ethylaniline)	-0.99	3.66	0.605	-8.181	0
75.	2-Amino-7-nitrofluorene	3.00	3.06	-1.164	-8.595	1
76.	Benzidine	-0.39	1.34	0.147	-7.931	0
77.	1-Amino-4-nitronaphthalene	-1.77	2.48	-1.035	-8.663	0
78.	4-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	1.02	2.68	-0.959	-8.630	0
79.	4-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	1.04	2.68	-1.102	-8.707	0
80.	1-Aminophenazine	-0.01	2.18	-1.164	-8.230	1
81.	4,4'-Methylenebis (<i>o</i> -fluoroaniline)	0.23	2.50	0.186	-8.467	0
82.	4-Chloro-2-nitroaniline	-2.22	2.72	-1.019	-9.110	0
83.	3-Aminoquinoline	-3.14	1.63	-0.376	-8.534	0
84.	3-Aminocarbazole	-0.48	2.30	-0.107	-7.877	1
85.	4-Chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine	-0.49	1.28	0.241	-8.325	0
86.	3-Aminophenanthrene	3.77	3.26	-0.203	-8.122	1
87.	3,4'-Diaminobiphenyl	0.20	1.58	0.103	-8.187	0
88.	1-Aminoanthracene	1.18	3.69	-0.804	-7.820	1
89.	1-Aminocarbazole	-1.04	2.30	-0.115	-8.035	1
90.	9-Aminoanthracene	0.87	3.26	-0.712	-7.600	1
91.	4-Aminocarbazole	-1.42	2.30	-0.029	-7.993	1
92.	6-Aminochrysene	1.83	4.98	-0.592	-7.926	1
93.	1-Aminopyrene	1.43	4.31	-0.700	-7.580	1
94.	4,4'-Methylenebis (<i>o</i> -isopropyl-aniline)	-1.77	4.46	0.610	-8.165	0
95.	2,7-Diaminophenazine	3.97	1.64	-1.069	-8.110	1

This model contained four compounds (35, 59, 74, 86) whose residues i.e. the difference between observed and calculated log TA98, were two times larger than their respective standard deviations. It seems that such compounds behave differently and may perhaps have different type of mechanism. Such compounds are treated as outliers, therefore, their deletion from regression analysis yielded the following model :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & -9.307 - 0.309 (\pm 0.579) J \\ & + 1.599 (\pm 0.372) \text{Jhstv} + 2.413 (\pm 0.633) {}^2\chi \\ & - 1.305 (\pm 0.651) {}^2\chi^v - 1.839 (\pm 0.603) {}^2\Delta \\ & + 1.811 (\pm 0.250) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$n = 84, \text{Se} = 0.824, R = 0.905, R^2A = 0.805, F = 58.048, Q = 1.098$$

This model [eq. (3)] is free from the existence of outlier. The negative coefficients of J, ${}^2\chi^v$ and ${}^2\Delta$ are probably due to co-linearity defect. Such a co-linearity defect and how to overcome them is discussed separately in the following part of results and discussion. All the four topological indices used in eq. (3) viz. J, Jhstv, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^2\chi^v$ and ${}^2\Delta$ are related to connectivity in the molecular graphs to the compound and that J and Jhstv account for extended connectivity. Therefore, according to these results connectivity is mainly responsible for the exhibition of mutagenic activity (log TA98). Though this model [eq. (3)] appears to be far better than the earlier reported¹² four parametric model, we can't make exact comparison as the earlier model is not further analyzed for the presence/absence of any outlier. However, this model [eq. (3)] did indicate that the mutagenic activity of the compounds

Table 3. Connectivity indices calculated for 95 compounds used in the present study

Compd. no.	${}^0\chi$	${}^1\chi$	${}^2\chi$	${}^0\chi^v$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^0\Delta$	${}^1\Delta$	${}^2\Delta$
1.	10.414	7.237	6.92	9.713	5.704	4.811	0.701	1.533	2.109
2.	7.560	4.736	4.064	6.218	3.139	2.245	1.342	1.597	1.819
3.	7.682	5.377	4.617	5.989	3.470	2.417	1.693	1.907	2.200
4.	7.397	4.826	3.915	6.002	3.310	2.002	1.395	1.516	1.913
5.	7.682	5.377	4.517	6.119	3.610	2.568	1.563	1.767	2.049
6.	9.544	6.860	6.190	7.826	4.817	3.715	1.718	2.043	2.473
7.	10.251	7.326	6.714	8.274	5.009	3.806	1.977	2.317	2.908
8.	11.405	8.360	7.676	9.274	5.771	4.479	2.131	2.589	3.197
9.	7.682	5.377	4.617	5.989	3.470	2.422	1.693	1.907	2.195
10.	11.121	7.737	7.242	8.619	5.059	3.825	2.502	2.678	3.417
11.	7.682	5.360	4.723	6.119	3.604	2.607	1.563	1.756	2.116
12.	11.405	8.343	7.751	9.533	6.044	4.805	1.872	2.299	2.946
13.	11.544	7.665	6.963	8.460	4.770	3.433	3.084	2.895	3.530
14.	7.724	4.609	4.381	6.732	3.443	2.793	0.992	1.166	1.588
15.	9.544	6.843	6.286	7.826	4.811	3.751	1.718	2.032	2.535
16.	11.707	7.575	7.055	9.887	5.437	4.287	1.820	2.138	2.768
17.	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.809	3.027	2.360	1.044	1.171	1.513
18.	10.414	7.237	6.920	8.326	5.011	4.010	2.088	2.226	2.910
19.	11.405	8.360	7.667	9.274	5.771	4.476	2.131	2.589	3.191
20.	9.544	6.843	6.286	7.826	4.811	3.751	1.718	2.032	2.535
21.	9.966	6.771	5.946	7.774	4.476	3.209	2.192	2.295	2.737
22.	9.096	6.360	5.418	7.274	4.271	2.988	1.822	2.089	2.430
23.	7.560	4.736	4.064	6.218	3.139	2.229	1.342	1.597	1.835
24.	9.544	6.843	6.286	7.619	4.604	3.476	1.925	2.239	2.810
25.	8.431	5.109	4.772	5.520	2.839	2.000	2.911	2.270	2.772
26.	9.966	6.788	5.851	7.774	4.482	3.175	2.192	2.306	2.676
27.	10.414	7.237	6.920	8.196	4.945	3.935	2.218	2.292	2.985
28.	10.251	7.360	6.522	8.481	5.289	4.013	1.770	2.071	2.509
29.	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.809	3.027	2.360	1.044	1.171	1.513
30.	11.544	7.682	6.876	8.460	4.776	3.396	3.084	2.906	3.480
31.	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.257	2.750	2.062	1.596	1.448	1.811
32.	10.251	7.326	6.714	8.119	4.854	3.601	2.132	2.472	3.113
33.	9.803	6.843	5.866	8.498	5.245	4.131	1.305	1.598	1.735
34.	10.008	6.020	5.702	6.337	3.204	2.257	3.671	2.816	3.445
35.	11.596	7.604	7.113	9.774	5.521	4.613	1.822	2.083	2.500
36.	6.853	4.198	3.873	4.565	2.405	1.666	2.288	1.793	2.207
37.	10.673	7.237	6.487	8.481	4.927	3.660	2.192	2.310	2.827
38.	11.707	7.575	7.055	9.619	5.303	4.143	2.088	2.272	2.912
39.	11.405	8.343	7.785	9.274	5.765	4.518	2.131	2.578	3.267
40.	13.121	8.575	7.862	9.146	5.070	3.615	3.975	3.505	4.247
41.	11.405	8.360	7.676	9.274	5.771	4.479	2.131	2.589	3.197
42.	11.380	7.737	6.829	9.188	5.427	3.983	2.192	2.310	2.846
43.	5.983	3.788	3.365	5.021	2.677	1.988	0.962	1.111	1.377
44.	10.251	7.343	6.628	8.533	5.284	4.084	1.718	2.059	2.544
45.	5.983	3.788	3.365	4.265	2.299	1.552	1.718	1.489	1.813
46.	10.251	7.360	6.534	8.533	5.300	4.029	1.718	2.060	2.505
47.	9.966	6.754	6.064	7.774	4.470	3.251	2.192	2.284	2.813
48.	11.405	8.326	7.857	9.533	6.028	4.875	1.872	2.298	2.982
49.	10.878	6.430	6.251	6.837	3.410	2.487	4.041	3.020	3.764
50.	12.698	8.631	8.310	10.157	5.926	4.646	2.541	2.705	3.664
51.	11.121	7.720	7.348	8.619	5.053	3.860	2.502	2.667	3.488
52.	7.682	5.360	4.723	5.989	3.464	2.456	1.693	1.896	2.267
53.	7.560	4.736	4.042	6.218	3.139	2.223	1.342	1.597	1.819
54.	11.544	7.665	6.963	8.460	4.770	3.433	3.084	2.895	3.530
55.	9.966	6.771	5.946	7.774	4.476	3.209	2.192	2.295	2.737
56.	11.121	7.754	7.136	8.619	5.065	3.790	2.502	2.689	3.346
57.	10.510	7.343	6.207	9.723	6.745	5.325	0.787	0.598	0.882

Table-3 (contd.)

58.	10.878	6.430	6.220	8.223	4.103	3.229	2.655	2.327	2.991
59.	12.795	8.754	7.444	10.602	6.433	4.651	2.193	2.321	2.793
60.	9.803	6.843	5.866	7.682	4.429	2.984	2.121	2.414	2.882
61.	9.096	6.377	5.324	7.274	4.277	2.953	1.822	2.100	2.371
62.	11.121	7.754	7.136	8.619	5.065	3.790	2.502	2.689	3.346
63.	9.544	6.860	6.180	7.826	4.817	3.707	1.718	2.034	2.473
64.	11.405	8.343	7.773	9.274	5.765	4.514	2.131	2.578	3.259
65.	5.983	3.805	3.239	5.021	2.683	1.929	0.962	1.122	1.310
66.	5.983	3.788	3.377	4.887	2.610	1.914	1.096	1.178	1.463
67.	10.129	6.698	6.084	7.305	4.115	2.982	2.824	2.583	3.102
68.	11.544	7.665	6.951	8.460	4.770	3.429	3.084	2.895	3.522
69.	5.983	3.788	3.365	5.851	3.092	2.467	0.132	0.696	0.898
70.	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.391	2.817	2.140	1.462	1.381	1.733
71.	13.121	8.651	7.437	10.435	5.528	3.913	2.686	3.123	3.524
72.	9.096	6.360	5.418	8.000	5.215	4.002	1.096	1.145	1.416
73.	9.803	6.834	5.866	7.682	4.429	2.984	2.121	2.405	1.405
74.	15.569	9.880	9.364	13.481	7.647	6.413	2.088	2.233	2.951
75.	11.991	8.148	7.819	9.012	5.311	4.192	2.979	2.837	3.627
76.	9.966	6.754	6.040	7.774	4.470	3.244	2.192	2.284	2.796
77.	10.129	6.698	6.075	7.305	4.115	2.977	2.824	2.583	3.098
78.	11.544	7.665	6.951	8.460	4.770	3.429	3.084	2.895	3.522
79.	11.544	7.665	6.939	8.460	4.770	3.426	3.084	2.895	3.513
80.	10.251	7.343	6.608	8.119	4.860	3.565	2.132	2.483	3.043
81.	12.414	8.059	7.503	9.082	5.138	3.889	3.332	2.921	3.614
82.	8.431	5.109	4.803	6.207	3.182	2.397	2.224	1.927	2.406
83.	7.682	5.360	4.723	5.989	3.464	2.461	1.693	1.896	2.262
84.	9.544	6.843	6.286	7.619	4.604	3.476	1.925	2.239	2.810
85.	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.521	2.882	2.210	1.332	1.316	1.663
86.	10.251	7.343	6.628	8.533	5.284	4.084	1.718	2.059	2.544
87.	9.966	6.754	6.052	7.774	4.470	3.247	2.192	2.284	2.805
88.	10.251	7.343	6.608	8.274	5.015	3.768	1.977	2.328	2.840
89.	9.544	6.860	6.180	7.619	4.610	3.440	1.925	2.250	2.740
90.	10.251	7.360	6.512	8.274	5.021	3.733	1.977	2.339	2.779
91.	9.544	6.860	6.190	7.619	4.610	3.440	1.925	2.250	2.750
92.	12.820	9.343	8.439	10.635	6.693	5.209	2.185	2.650	3.230
93.	11.405	8.343	7.739	9.533	6.044	4.800	1.872	2.299	2.939
94.	15.569	9.880	9.364	13.481	7.647	6.413	2.088	2.233	2.951
95.	11.121	7.720	7.348	8.619	5.053	3.860	2.502	2.667	3.488

under present study can be modeled quite well without using the hydrophobic parameter i.e. log P.

(ii) Modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) by adding log P term to the topological indices :

Though in the earlier section (i) we argued that we can do well in modeling log TA98 without using log P, we have attempted such modeling containing the combinations of log P with the topological indices. Once again, as in our previous study¹² we have used 88 compounds here also we used the same for the present study.

For the set of 88 compounds (which was used in our earlier study) we obtained the following penta-parametric model [eq. (4)] for modeling the mutagenic activity (log TA98). This model [eq. (4)] in addition to log P and the indicator parameter IL contains J, Jhetz and $^1\Delta$ as the

correlating parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & -2.363 + 0.836 (\pm 0.118) \log P \\ & - 2.86 (\pm 0.840) J + 1.292 (\pm 0.512) \text{Jhetz} \\ & + 0.618 (\pm 0.171) ^1\Delta + 1.864 (\pm 0.241) \text{IL} \quad (4) \\ n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.830, R = 0.903, R^2_A = 0.805, F = \\ & 73.446, Q = 1.088 \end{aligned}$$

The parameters involved in eq. (4) indicated that the hydrophobicity is quite favorable for modeling the mutagenic activity (log TA98). The statistics involved is superior to the earlier tetra-parametric as well as the hexa-parametric model discussed above. It is worthy to mention that this model [eq. (4)] does not contain any outlier. This is an additional factor in favor of eq. (4) over that of eq. (3).

We have also investigated the influence of the addition of E_{HOMO} or/and E_{LUMO} to the above model [eq.

Table 4. Balaban and Balaban type indices calculated for the set of 95 compounds used in the present study

Compd. no.	W	J	Jhetz	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete	Jhetp	BAC
1.	337	1.722	2.449	2.451	2.340	2.381	2.340	5
2.	116	2.356	3.302	3.302	2.453	3.298	2.328	11
3.	140	1.993	3.035	3.035	2.698	3.030	2.628	2
4.	127	2.132	2.976	2.975	1.999	2.971	1.872	7
5.	140	1.993	2.945	2.945	2.821	2.944	2.789	2
6.	265	1.800	2.525	2.525	2.455	2.525	2.436	2
7.	342	1.673	2.490	2.490	2.432	2.489	2.416	2
8.	427	1.694	2.522	2.522	2.467	2.522	2.452	2
9.	140	1.993	3.043	3.042	2.681	3.038	2.608	2
10.	405	1.701	2.293	2.293	1.752	2.287	1.645	5
11.	144	1.932	2.858	2.858	2.744	2.857	2.715	2
12.	424	1.692	2.405	2.405	2.354	2.405	2.341	2
13.	441	1.879	2.785	2.784	2.341	2.782	2.237	11
14.	111	2.462	3.322	3.322	3.169	3.321	3.131	17
15.	272	1.751	2.460	2.460	2.395	2.460	3.378	2
16.	440	1.884	2.857	2.860	2.616	2.761	2.624	17
17.	84	2.346	3.217	3.217	3.043	3.215	2.999	10
18.	337	1.722	2.381	2.381	2.277	2.380	2.250	5
19.	431	1.679	2.500	2.500	2.447	2.500	2.433	2
20.	274	1.739	2.422	2.422	2.360	2.421	2.344	2
21.	301	1.867	2.751	2.751	2.613	2.750	2.578	5
22.	252	1.789	2.659	2.659	2.585	2.658	2.566	2
23.	115	2.376	3.327	3.326	2.466	3.322	2.340	11
24.	274	1.739	2.488	2.487	2.195	2.485	2.130	2
25.	152	2.396	3.492	3.491	2.380	3.483	2.186	18
26.	287	1.963	2.888	2.888	2.731	2.886	2.691	5
27.	337	1.722	2.391	2.391	2.235	2.390	2.203	5
28.	326	1.763	2.371	2.371	2.317	2.370	2.302	2
29.	84	2.346	3.218	3.218	3.041	3.216	2.997	10
30.	429	1.944	2.879	2.879	2.401	2.876	2.290	11
31.	84	2.346	3.300	3.300	2.797	3.297	2.706	10
32.	342	1.673	2.263	2.263	1.743	2.258	1.640	2
33.	329	1.685	2.912	2.913	2.194	2.230	2.504	2
34.	240	2.526	3.693	3.692	2.374	3.681	2.144	30
35.	429	1.940	2.436	2.436	2.394	2.436	2.382	10
36.	84	2.346	3.447	3.474	2.408	3.430	2.168	10
37.	404	1.681	2.166	2.166	2.091	2.165	2.071	5
38.	440	1.884	2.720	2.720	2.616	2.719	2.588	17
39.	432	1.674	2.493	2.493	2.441	2.493	2.427	2
40.	617	1.897	2.821	2.821	2.211	2.817	2.076	21
41.	426	1.700	2.531	2.531	2.475	2.531	2.461	2
42.	508	1.601	1.980	1.980	1.924	1.980	1.909	5
43.	62	2.192	3.345	3.352	2.888	3.160	2.901	5
44.	334	1.722	2.306	2.306	2.256	2.305	2.245	2
45.	62	2.192	3.211	3.225	2.502	3.201	2.320	5
46.	322	1.787	2.433	2.433	2.374	2.432	2.358	2
47.	301	1.861	2.743	2.743	2.606	2.742	2.511	5
48.	434	1.654	2.343	2.343	2.297	2.343	2.284	2
49.	282	2.704	3.916	3.916	2.539	3.904	2.298	41
50.	605	1.612	2.180	2.180	1.907	2.177	1.846	12
51.	413	1.667	2.252	2.252	1.729	2.246	1.625	5
52.	144	1.932	2.943	2.942	2.627	2.938	2.561	2
53.	117	2.330	3.268	3.267	2.442	3.264	2.318	11
54.	441	1.879	2.785	2.784	2.341	2.782	2.237	11
55.	301	1.867	2.751	2.751	2.613	2.750	2.578	5
56.	396	1.739	2.339	2.338	1.778	2.332	1.668	5
57.	420	1.601	3.124	3.125	2.052	2.072	2.550	2

Table-4 (contd.)

58.	286	2.661	4.007	4.011	2.582	3.847	2.359	41
59.	736	1.543	1.796	1.796	1.756	1.795	1.745	5
60.	329	1.685	2.412	2.411	1.539	2.408	1.432	2
61.	240	1.885	2.797	2.797	2.710	2.796	2.688	2
62.	395	1.744	2.343	2.343	1.781	2.337	1.670	5
63.	267	1.786	2.479	2.479	2.413	2.479	2.396	2
64.	437	1.656	2.467	2.467	2.416	2.466	2.402	2
65.	60	2.279	3.484	3.491	2.977	3.276	2.992	5
66.	61	2.231	3.131	3.131	2.927	3.129	2.877	5
67.	272	2.092	3.083	3.083	2.425	3.078	2.283	11
68.	462	1.793	2.660	2.660	2.257	2.657	2.160	11
69.	62	2.192	3.432	3.442	2.981	3.136	2.980	5
70.	84	2.346	3.535	3.540	2.797	3.368	2.751	10
71.	613	1.913	2.793	2.792	2.236	2.790	2.147	21
72.	252	1.789	2.112	2.112	2.064	2.112	2.052	2
73.	329	1.685	2.412	2.411	1.539	2.408	1.432	2
74.	976	1.867	2.313	2.313	2.264	2.313	2.252	41
75.	495	1.674	2.333	2.333	2.003	2.331	1.923	11
76.	315	1.780	2.627	2.627	2.504	2.626	2.473	5
77.	274	2.079	3.066	3.066	2.421	3.062	2.280	11
78.	450	1.843	2.732	2.732	2.305	2.729	2.203	11
79.	471	1.760	2.612	2.612	2.223	2.609	2.129	11
80.	334	1.714	2.312	2.312	1.771	2.306	1.664	2
81.	552	1.775	2.308	2.313	2.049	2.305	1.971	17
82.	148	2.471	3.708	3.712	2.546	3.576	2.377	18
83.	144	1.932	2.959	2.959	2.621	2.954	2.555	2
84.	272	1.751	2.518	2.518	2.248	2.515	2.186	2
85.	84	2.346	3.494	3.500	2.922	3.333	2.891	10
86.	330	1.741	2.323	2.323	2.272	2.322	2.259	2
87.	308	1.820	2.684	2.684	2.554	2.683	2.521	5
88.	334	1.714	2.549	2.549	2.486	2.548	2.469	2
89.	267	1.786	2.549	2.549	2.240	2.546	2.171	2
90.	326	1.760	2.616	2.616	2.546	2.615	2.528	2
91.	265	1.800	2.585	2.585	2.302	2.583	2.237	2
92.	620	1.575	2.051	2.051	2.016	2.051	2.011	2
93.	428	1.677	2.387	2.387	2.338	2.387	2.325	2
94.	976	1.867	2.313	2.313	2.264	2.313	2.252	41
95.	414	1.664	2.249	2.249	1.727	2.243	1.623	5

(4)]. Our results as given below indicate that addition of E_{HOMO} is more favorable than the addition of E_{LUMO} . Furthermore, when both the parameters are added to the above eq. (4) the statistics is not improved over the addition of E_{HOMO} to the eq. (4). This is made more clear by considering the following models :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & -3.451 + 1.000 (\pm 0.131) \log P \\ & + 0.305 (\pm 0.239) E_{\text{LUMO}} - 3.163 (\pm 0.981) J \\ & + 1.710 (\pm 0.672) \text{Jhetz} - 0.721 (\pm 0.221) {}^1\Delta \\ & + 2.156 (\pm 0.277) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.843, R = 0.905, R^2A = 0.806, F = 61.092, Q = 1.074$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & 1.685 + 1.051 (\pm 0.130) \log P \\ & + 0.724 (\pm 0.298) E_{\text{HOMO}} - 2.098 (\pm 0.855) J \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & + 1.284 (\pm 0.512) \text{Jhetz} + 0.689 (\pm 0.178) {}^1\Delta \\ & + 1.846 (\pm 0.247) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.822, R = 0.910, R^2A = 0.815, F = 64.948, Q = 1.107$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & 2.602 + 1.049 (\pm 0.131) \log P \\ & - 0.121 (\pm 0.311) E_{\text{LUMO}} + 0.826 (\pm 0.398) E_{\text{HOMO}} \\ & - 1.791 (\pm 1.168) J + 1.086 (\pm 0.724) \text{Jhetz} \\ & + 0.639 (\pm 0.221) {}^1\Delta + 1.760 (\pm 0.333) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.826, R = 0.910, R^2A = 0.813, F = 55.108, Q = 1.101$$

Statistically, the models expressed by eqs. (5) and (7) are less favorable as they contain one or more correlating parameters whose coefficients are either smaller than their

Table 5. Correlation matrix

	log TA98	log P	E _{LUMO}	E _{HOMO}	IL	W	J	Jhetz
log TA98	1.000							
log P	0.633	1.000						
E _{LUMO}	-0.470	-0.302	1.000					
E _{HOMO}	0.346	0.123	0.312	1.000				
IL	0.750	0.438	-0.383	0.450	1.000			
W	0.393	0.466	-0.169	0.230	0.215	1.000		
J	-0.605	-0.397	0.197	-0.550	-0.569	-0.593	1.000	
Jhetz	-0.548	-0.380	0.029	-0.538	-0.576	-0.642	0.920	1.000
Jhetm	-0.548	-0.381	0.030	-0.538	-0.576	-0.643	0.920	0.999
Jhetv	-0.305	-0.056	0.260	-0.174	-0.374	-0.549	0.600	0.650
Jhete	-0.532	-0.370	0.057	-0.560	-0.541	-0.644	0.950	0.955
Jhetp	-0.213	0.013	0.270	-0.049	-0.279	-0.470	0.422	0.513
BAC	-0.265	-0.005	0.018	-0.423	-0.413	0.320	0.536	0.410
⁰ χ	0.486	0.488	-0.304	0.199	0.290	0.965	-0.577	-0.612
¹ χ	0.614	0.558	-0.349	0.328	0.460	0.925	-0.740	-0.744
² χ	0.634	0.560	-0.376	0.296	0.495	0.918	-0.689	-0.708
⁰ χ ^v	0.511	0.567	-0.165	0.350	0.345	0.950	-0.650	-0.684
¹ χ ^v	0.595	0.615	-0.206	0.435	0.465	0.894	-0.771	-0.767
² χ ^v	0.595	0.636	-0.180	0.435	0.487	0.864	-0.714	-0.723
⁰ Δ	0.158	0.029	-0.484	-0.280	-0.004	0.478	-0.080	-0.103
¹ Δ	0.413	0.221	-0.501	-0.019	0.268	0.627	-0.388	-0.404
² Δ	0.448	0.234	-0.530	0.008	0.340	0.654	-0.381	-0.410
	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete	Jhetp	BAC	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ
Jhetm	1.000							
Jhetv	0.650	1.000						
Jhete	0.955	0.665	1.000					
Jhetp	0.513	0.928	0.473	1.000				
BAC	0.409	0.095	0.438	-0.021	1.000			
⁰ χ	-0.613	-0.560	-0.599	-0.497	0.328	1.000		
¹ χ	-0.745	-0.601	-0.734	-0.504	0.090	0.966	1.000	
² χ	-0.709	-0.576	-0.689	-0.492	0.156	0.968	0.988	1.000
⁰ χ ^v	-0.685	-0.501	-0.708	-0.385	0.215	0.946	0.941	0.935
¹ χ ^v	-0.768	-0.529	-0.813	-0.373	0.014	0.890	0.941	0.923
² χ ^v	-0.723	-0.455	-0.777	-0.296	0.056	0.856	0.899	0.899
⁰ Δ	-0.104	-0.399	-0.003	-0.503	0.428	0.594	0.503	0.526
¹ Δ	-0.405	-0.514	-0.282	-0.575	0.210	0.744	0.727	0.735
² Δ	-0.411	-0.474	-0.296	-0.528	0.253	0.769	0.746	0.775
	⁰ χ ^v	¹ χ ^v	² χ ^v	⁰ Δ	¹ Δ	² Δ		
⁰ χ ^v	1.000							
¹ χ ^v	0.970	1.000						
² χ ^v	0.960	0.986	1.000					
⁰ Δ	0.299	0.209	0.135	1.000				
¹ Δ	0.515	0.454	0.370	0.905	1.000			
² Δ	0.557	0.497	0.436	0.875	0.961	1.000		

standard deviation or considerably less than two times the standard deviations. Such models are not allowed statistically²⁰. In the light of this it is interesting to compare these results with the results obtained earlier in the tetra-parametric model¹². The earlier model¹² is given below :

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{TA98} = & 7.20 + 1.08 (\pm 0.26) \log P \\ & + 1.28 (\pm 0.64) E_{\text{HOMO}} - 0.73 (\pm 0.41) E_{\text{LUMO}} \\ & + 1.46 (\pm 0.56) \text{IL} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$n = 88, \text{Se} = 0.860, R = 0.898, F = 12.600, Q = 1.104$$

Table 6. Regression parameters and quality of correlations attempted under three categories :
(i) without log P; (ii) with log P and (iii) Balaban and Balaban type indices for modeling log TA98

Without log P :

Sl. no.	Parameter (s)	R	Se	R ² A	F
1.	IL	0.7501	1.2799	-	119.644
2.	IL, ¹ χ	0.8092	1.1433	0.6473	87.244
3.	IL, W, ¹ χ	0.8268	1.1005	0.6732	65.539
4.	IL, W, Jhetv, ¹ χ	0.8389	1.0710	0.6905	53.429
5.	IL, W, Jhetv, E _{LUMO} , ¹ χ	0.8434	1.0016	0.6959	44.021
6.	E _{LUMO} , IL, W, Jhetv, ¹ χ, ² Δ	0.8478	1.0551	0.6996	37.488
7.	E _{LUMO} , IL, W, Jhetv, ¹ χ, ² χ, ² Δ	0.8501	1.0539	0.7003	32.377
8.	E _{LUMO} , IL, W, Jhetv, ¹ χ, ² χ, ² χ ^v , ² Δ	0.8560	1.0404	0.7079	29.476
9.	E _{LUMO} , IL, W, J, Jhetv, ¹ χ ^v , ² χ, ² χ ^v , ² Δ	0.8594	1.0350	0.7109	26.686

With log P :

1.	IL	0.7501	1.2799	-	119.644
2.	log P, IL	0.8228	1.1059	0.6700	96.413
3.	log P, IL, ¹ Δ	0.8426	1.0536	0.7005	74.277
4.	log P, IL, J, ¹ Δ	0.8493	1.0386	0.7089	58.228
5.	log P, IL, J, Jhetz, ¹ Δ	0.8585	1.0147	0.7222	49.869

Role of Balaban indices :

1.	J	-0.6057	1.5400	-	39.796
2.	Jhetz	-0.5474	1.6196	-	39.796
3.	Jhetm	-0.5479	1.6190	-	39.904
4.	Jhetv	-0.3051	1.8431	-	9.543
5.	Jhete	-0.5320	1.6387	-	36.718
6.	Jhetp	-0.2134	1.8908	-	4.437
7.	BAC	-0.2645	1.8669	-	6.997
8.	J, IL	0.7810	1.2152	0.6010	71.941
9.	Jhetz, IL	0.7633	1.2571	0.5738	64.211
10.	Jhetm, IL	0.7631	1.2568	0.5738	64.268
11.	Jhetv, IL	0.7506	1.2858	0.5539	57.350
12.	Jhete, IL	0.7650	1.2533	0.5761	64.887
13.	Jhetp, IL	0.7501	1.2868	0.5532	59.784
14.	BAC, IL	0.7518	1.2832	0.5557	59.787
15.	J, Jhetz, IL	0.7883	1.2037	0.6099	49.802
16.	J, Jhetm, IL	0.7881	1.2043	0.6086	49.726
17.	J, Jhetv, IL	0.7871	1.2069	0.6060	49.379
18.	J, Jhete, IL	0.7937	1.1901	0.6178	51.657
19.	J, Jhetp, IL	0.7843	1.2137	0.6025	48.493
20.	J, BAC, IL	0.7953	1.1862	0.6203	52.191
21.	J, Jhetz, Jhetm, IL	0.7933	1.1979	0.6128	38.193
22.	J, Jhetz, Jhetv, IL	0.7912	1.2030	0.6095	37.672
23.	J, Jhetz, Jhete, IL	0.7939	1.1961	0.6139	38.368
24.	J, Jhetz, Jhetp, IL	0.7892	1.2082	0.6061	37.158
25.	J, Jhetz, BAC, IL	0.8104	1.1527	0.6414	43.042
26.	J, Jhetm, Jhetv, IL	0.7911	1.2035	0.6092	37.627
27.	J, Jhetm, Jhete, IL	0.7939	1.1962	0.6139	38.358
28.	J, Jhetm, Jhetp, IL	0.7890	1.2087	0.6058	37.109
29.	J, Jhetm, BAC, IL	0.8101	1.1534	0.6410	42.961
30.	J, Jhetv, Jhete, IL	0.7951	1.1931	0.6159	38.682
31.	J, Jhetv, Jhetp, IL	0.7886	1.2097	0.6051	37.013
32.	J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	0.8111	1.1508	0.6427	43.264
33.	J, Jhete, Jhetp, IL	0.7946	1.1944	0.6151	38.548
34.	J, Jhete, BAC, IL	0.8178	1.1323	0.6541	45.431
35.	J, Jhetp, BAC, IL	0.8058	1.1650	0.6338	41.671

In this model also the coefficient of E_{LUMO} is smaller than two times its standard deviation and is thus not that favorable. Another interesting aspect to be considered is the coefficients of $\log P$ term. In our earlier report¹² the coefficients of $\log P$ in eqs. (3), (3a), (3c) and (3d) are found as 1.08, 1.69, 1.09 and 1.15 respectively. In the present study, expressed by eqs. (4), (5), (6) and (7), the coefficients of $\log P$ are observed as 0.837, 1.000, 1.051 and 1.049 respectively. This shows that compared to our earlier study¹², the coefficients of $\log P$ in the present study is much more nearer to one. Thus, the present results appear to be much more interesting for mutagenesis.

(iii) Modeling of mutagenic activity ($\log TA98$) using Balaban and Balaban type indices alone :

We now discuss modeling of $\log TA98$ using Balaban and Balaban type indices alone for the same set of 88 compounds used for the set of 88 compounds the best model is the one consisting of J, Jhetv, BAC and IL as the correlating parameters :

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & 1.038 - 4.083 (\pm 0.684) J \\ & + 1.585 (\pm 0.434) Jhetv + 0.074 (\pm 0.017) BAC \\ & + 2.718 (\pm 0.283) IL \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$n = 88, Se = 1.038, R = 0.848, R^2A = 0.705, F = 53.038, Q = 0.817$$

The physical significance of the parameters involved in this eq. (9) is the same as before. This model contains five outliers, they are, therefore, deleted from regression analysis for the aforementioned reasons. The deletion of which gave the following model with much improved statistics and without containing any outlier :

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & 2.542 - 5.140 (\pm 0.643) J \\ & + 2.203 (\pm 0.399) Jhetv + 0.116 (\pm 0.018) BAC \\ & + 2.778 (\pm 0.252) IL \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$n = 83, Se = 0.889, R = 0.888, R^2A = 0.779, F = 73.305, Q = 0.999$$

Like the earlier cases [Section (ii)] it will be interesting to investigate the influence of the addition of $\log P$, E_{LUMO} , E_{HOMO} and both E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} to the above model [eq. (10)]. When we did so, the following models with improved statistics resulted :

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & - 0.279 + 0.864 (\pm 0.152) \log P \\ & - 2.303 (\pm 0.661) J + 0.594 (\pm 0.408) Jhetv \\ & + 0.037 (\pm 0.016) BAC \\ & + 2.083 (\pm 0.265) IL \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$n = 88, Se = 0.884, R = 0.894, R^2A = 0.786, F = 65.022, Q = 1.011$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & - 0.255 + 0.799 (\pm 0.155) \log P \\ & - 0.293 (\pm 0.175) E_{LUMO} - 2.412 (\pm 0.657) J \\ & + 0.726 (\pm 0.411) Jhetv + 0.034 (\pm 0.016) BAC \\ & + 1.977 (\pm 0.275) IL \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$n = 88, Se = 0.874, R = 0.895, R^2A = 0.791, F = 55.831, Q = 1.024$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & 1.655 + 0.917 (\pm 0.164) \log P \\ & + 0.278 (\pm 0.322) E_{HOMO} - 1.999 (\pm 0.750) J \\ & + 0.472 (\pm 0.433) Jhetv + 0.036 (\pm 0.016) BAC \\ & + 2.009 (\pm 0.279) IL \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$n = 88, Se = 0.885, R = 0.895, R^2A = 0.786, F = 54.140, Q = 1.011$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log TA98 = & 6.268 + 0.907 (\pm 0.157) \log P - 0.601 \\ & (\pm 0.213) E_{LUMO} + 0.934 (\pm 0.387) E_{HOMO} \\ & - 1.511 (\pm 0.740) J + 0.453 (\pm 0.411) Jhetv \\ & + 0.030 (\pm 0.016) BAC \\ & + 1.617 (\pm 0.302) IL \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$n = 88, Se = 0.850, R = 0.905, R^2A = 0.803, F = 51.538, Q = 1.065$$

These eqs. (11)–(14) show that when Balaban and Balaban type indices are used for modeling the mutagenic activity ($\log TA98$) the addition of all the three terms viz. $\log P$, E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} exhibit their favorable contributions in modeling the activity.

Predictive power of the model :

It is worthy to mention that excellent statistical parameters of the model do not necessary mean that it will also have excellent predictive power. Hence, we have investigated the predictive power of proposed models. There are two different ways to investigate the predictive power of the model. First one consists of calculating Pogliani quality factor²⁴⁻²⁶, Q . This quality factor Q is defined as the ratio of correlation coefficient to its standard error of estimation i.e. $Q = R/Se$. Thus, higher the value of R , the lower the Se , the greater will be the value of Q and more will be the predictive power of the model. The calculated values of Q are presented with the proposed models. In case of category (i) where in only topological indices are used, the model expressed by eq. (3) has the largest Q value (1.0984) and thus the highest predictive power. Similarly, in other two categories i.e.

Table 7. Comparison of the calculated mutagenicity (log TA98) from eqs. (3), (6) and (14) with there observed

Comps.	Actual log TA98	Eq. (3)		Eq. (6)		Eq. (14)	
		Pred. log TA98	Residue	Pred. log TA98	Residue	Pred. log TA98	Residue
1	2.620	2.255	0.365	2.280	0.340	2.605	0.015
2	-2.050	-2.582	0.532	-2.202	0.152	-2.411	0.361
3	-2.000	-1.668	-0.332	-2.141	0.141	-2.008	0.008
4	-2.300	-3.454	1.154	-2.539	0.239	-2.660	0.360
5	-0.600	-1.632	1.032	-0.999	-0.5001	-0.816	0.216
6	1.130	1.414	-0.284	1.268	-0.138	1.174	-0.044
7	2.620	1.762	0.858	2.547	0.073	2.595	0.025
8	2.880	2.723	0.157	2.986	-0.106	2.775	0.105
9	-1.140	-1.693	0.553	-1.279	0.139	-1.261	0.121
10	0.750	0.979	-0.229	0.622	0.128	0.823	-0.073
11	-0.670	-1.413	0.743	-1.045	0.375	-0.840	0.170
12	3.160	2.760	0.400	2.892	0.268	3.025	0.135
13	-0.550	-0.314	-0.236	-0.238	-0.312	-0.343	-0.207
14	-1.320	-0.995	-0.325	-1.843	0.523	-1.365	0.045
15	0.890	1.404	-0.514	1.224	-0.334	1.164	-0.274
16	0.810	0.633	0.177	0.684	0.126	0.802	0.008
17	-2.220	-1.683	-0.537	-2.531	0.311	-2.175	-0.045
18	0.480	1.726	-1.246	0.444	0.036	0.561	-0.081
19	3.310	2.689	0.621	3.604	-0.294	3.321	-0.011
20	1.930	1.352	0.578	1.827	0.103	1.733	0.197
21	-0.620	-0.579	-0.041	-0.707	0.087	-0.361	-0.259
22	-0.140	-1.021	0.881	-0.188	0.048	-0.352	0.212
23	-1.960	-2.575	0.615	-2.317	0.357	-2.571	0.611
24	0.600	0.941	-0.341	1.232	-0.632	0.894	-0.294
25	-2.520	-2.435	-0.085	-2.414	-0.106	-2.396	-0.124
26	-1.520	-0.493	-1.027	-1.404	-0.116	-1.686	0.166
27	0.410	1.619	-1.209	0.914	-0.504	0.897	-0.487
28	2.380	1.551	0.829	1.846	0.534	1.912	0.468
29	-2.400	-1.686	-0.714	-2.456	0.056	-2.133	-0.267
30	-0.920	-0.308	-0.612	-0.099	-0.821	-0.513	-0.407
31	-2.100	-2.236	0.136	-2.770	0.670	-2.669	0.569
32	0.550	0.551	-0.001	0.774	-0.224	0.955	-0.405
33	0.310	-0.746	1.056	-0.166	0.476	-0.302	0.612
34	-2.000	-1.814	-0.186	-2.185	0.185	-2.279	0.279
35	-3.000	-	-	-2.521	-0.479	-2.278	-0.722
36	-2.700	-3.069	0.369	-2.248	-0.452	-2.555	-0.145
37	-1.600	-0.805	-0.795	-1.785	0.185	-1.803	0.203
38	0.010	0.556	-0.546	-0.447	0.437	-0.221	0.211
39	3.230	2.771	0.459	2.920	0.310	2.707	0.523
40	-0.890	0.086	-0.976	0.230	-1.120	-0.081	-0.809
41	3.350	2.734	0.616	3.004	0.346	2.747	0.603
42	-2.150	-0.678	-1.472	-1.320	-0.830	-1.317	-0.833
43	-2.520	-2.374	-0.146	-2.077	-0.443	-2.049	-0.471
44	2.460	1.565	0.895	1.767	0.693	1.857	0.603
45	-3.320	-3.224	-0.096	-2.750	-0.570	-2.874	-0.446
46	2.980	1.650	1.330	2.207	0.773	2.209	0.771
47	-1.300	-0.498	-0.802	-1.551	0.251	-1.668	0.368
48	3.500	2.779	0.721	2.670	0.830	2.779	0.721
49	-0.690	-1.167	0.477	-0.917	0.227	-1.433	0.743
50	1.180	2.306	-1.126	0.921	0.259	0.967	0.213
51	1.120	1.033	0.087	0.431	0.689	0.599	0.521
52	-2.670	-1.681	-0.989	-2.047	-0.623	-1.891	-0.779
53	-3.000	-2.615	-0.385	-2.513	-0.487	-2.596	-0.404
54	-1.300	-0.314	-0.986	-0.140	-1.160	-0.449	-0.851

Table-7 (contd.)

55	-0.920	-0.579	-0.341	-1.351	0.431	-1.518	0.598
56	0.200	0.930	-0.730	0.697	-0.497	0.899	-0.699
57	-1.030	-0.114	-0.916	-1.099	0.069	-0.220	-0.810
58	-0.540	-0.706	0.166	-1.476	0.936	-1.166	0.626
59	-2.700	-	-	-1.669	-1.031	-1.524	-1.176
60	-1.140	-2.406	1.266	-1.570	0.430	-2.102	0.962
61	-1.490	-0.923	-0.567	-0.330	-1.160	-0.628	-0.862
62	0.040	0.933	-0.893	0.670	-0.630	0.854	-0.814
63	0.430	1.337	-0.907	1.584	-1.154	1.436	-1.006
64	3.800	2.728	1.072	3.002	0.798	2.803	0.997
65	-3.000	-2.362	-0.638	-2.099	-0.901	-2.172	-0.828
66	-0.800	-2.356	1.556	-2.292	1.492	-1.918	1.118
67	-1.170	-0.991	-0.179	-0.233	-0.937	-0.403	-0.767
68	0.690	-0.431	1.121	-0.275	0.965	-0.238	0.928
69	-2.700	-1.969	-0.731	-1.889	-0.811	-1.667	-1.033
70	-3.000	-2.194	-0.806	-2.000	-1.000	-2.103	-0.897
71	0.150	0.036	0.114	-0.424	0.574	-0.735	0.885
72	-1.240	-1.312	0.072	-0.795	-0.445	-0.324	-0.916
73	0.380	0.310	0.070	-0.206	0.586	-1.015	1.395
74	-0.990	-	-	0.204	-1.194	1.022	-2.012
75	3.000	1.916	1.084	1.966	1.034	2.046	0.954
76	-0.390	-0.654	0.264	-1.433	1.043	-1.414	1.024
77	-1.770	-1.002	-0.768	-0.622	-1.148	-0.661	-1.109
78	1.020	-0.370	1.390	-0.107	1.127	-0.191	1.211
79	1.040	-0.484	1.524	-0.143	1.183	-0.088	1.128
80	-0.010	0.503	-0.493	0.950	-0.940	1.152	-1.142
81	0.230	-0.196	0.426	-0.562	0.792	-0.724	0.954
82	-2.220	-1.963	-0.257	-1.143	-1.077	-1.196	-1.024
83	-3.140	-1.688	-1.452	-1.724	-1.416	-1.666	-1.474
84	-0.480	1.022	-1.502	1.351	-1.831	1.115	-1.595
85	-0.490	-1.957	1.467	-2.522	2.032	-2.408	1.918
86	3.770	-	-	1.829	1.941	1.842	1.928
87	0.200	-0.578	0.778	-1.377	1.577	-1.446	1.646
88	1.180	1.755	-0.575	3.032	-1.852	3.013	-1.833

(ii) and (iii) the models expressed by eqs. (6) and (14) have the largest Q values and thus, have the corresponding highest predictive powers. Still better way of deciding predictive power of the model is to calculate predictive correlation coefficient i.e. R^2_{Pred}

This can be done by calculating the mutagenic activity (log TA98) from the proposed models and comparing the same with the experimental activity. Such a comparison is shown in Table 7 and demonstrated in Figs. 1-3 using the results of [eqs. (3), (6) and (14)] respectively. The R^2_{Pred} values are found to be 0.8189, 0.8278 and 0.8187 respectively for these equations showing that these models, more or less, have similar predictive power and that the model expressed by eq. (6) having slightly better predictive power.

Cross-validation :

The essential feature of multiple regression analysis is

cross-validation which assesses the predictivity of the computed model²⁰. Cross-validation provides the values of PRESS, SSY, S_{PRESS} , R^2_{CV} and PSE from which we can investigate the predictive power of the proposed model. The meaning of these cross-validated parameters is given as a footnote to the Table 8.

It is argued that PRESS is a good estimate of the real prediction error of the model and if it is smaller than SSY the model predicts better than chance and can be considered "statistically" significant. Furthermore, the ratio PRESS/SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compound. To be a reasonable QSAR model PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4 and the value of this ratio smaller than 0.1 indicates an excellent model. Also, if PRESS value is transformed in a dimensionless term by relating it to the initial sum of squares, we obtain R^2_{CV} (Q^2) i.e. the comple-

Fig. 1. Correlation of observed and estimated log TA98 using eq. (3).

ment to the traces of unexplained variance over the total variance. Thus, PRESS and R^2_{CV} have good properties. However, for practical purposes of end users, the use of square-root of PRESS/N, which is called predictive square error (PSE) is more directly related to the uncertainty of the predictions. This parameter, namely PSE is much

more useful when S_{PRESS} (uncertainty of prediction) comes out to be the same as S_e (standard error of estimation). All cross-validated parameters given in Table 8 are in accordance with the aforementioned findings. It is interesting to mention that in the present case S_{PRESS} is found to be the same as that of S_e . Thus, the uncertainty in

Fig. 2. Correlation of observed and estimated log TA98 using eq. (6).

Fig. 3. Correlation of observed and estimated log TA98 using eq. (14).

prediction is decided by PSE. The PSE values also support our results discussed above.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) :

The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) is yet another parameter used to decide predictive power of the proposed models²⁰. This parameter is calculated using the following expression :

$$PE = \frac{2}{3} \frac{1-r^2}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (15)$$

where r^2 is the coefficient of variance and n is the number of compounds used in the proposed model. We have calculated PE value of all the proposed models and recorded them in Table 9. It is argued that if

- (i) $r < PE$, then correlation is not significant;
- (ii) $r > PE$, several times (at least three times), then correlation is indicated;
- (iii) $r > 6PE$, then the correlation is definitely good.

The data presented in Table 8 indicates that in all the

Table 8. Cross-validated parameters for the proposed models

Model	Parameters	n	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R^2_{CV}	S_{PRESS}	PSE	R^2_A
1	W, $^1\chi$, Jhetv, IL	95	103.266	245.124	0.4211	0.5789	1.070	1.0423	0.69
2	J, Jhetv, $^2\chi$, $^2\chi^y$, $^2\Delta$, IL	88	75.780	242.317	0.3173	0.6873	0.9672	0.9279	0.744
3	J, Jhetv, $^2\chi$, $^2\chi^y$, $^2\Delta$, IL	84	52.109	235.699	0.2210	0.7789	0.8226	0.7876	0.805
4	log P, J, Jhetz, $^1\Delta$, IL	88	57.200	253.082	0.2260	0.7740	0.8352	0.8062	0.805
5	log P, E_{LUMO} , J, Jhetz, $^1\Delta$, IL	88	57.570	260.527	0.2210	0.7790	0.8378	0.8088	0.806
6	log P, E_{HOMO} , J, Jhetz, $^1\Delta$, IL	88	54.741	263.357	0.2078	0.7921	0.8171	0.7887	0.815
7	log P, E_{LUMO} , E_{HOMO} , J, Jhetz, $^1\Delta$, IL	88	54.638	263.460	0.2074	0.7926	0.8264	0.7880	0.813
8	J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	88	89.452	228.645	0.3912	0.6088	1.0381	1.0082	0.705
9	J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	83	61.638	231.714	0.2662	0.5734	0.8889	0.8618	0.779
10	log P, J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	88	64.071	254.026	0.2522	0.7478	0.8839	0.8532	0.786
11	log P, E_{LUMO} , J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	88	61.939	256.158	0.2418	0.7582	0.8745	0.8390	0.791
12	log P, E_{HOMO} , J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	88	63.488	254.609	0.2494	0.7506	0.8853	0.8494	0.786
13	log P, E_{LUMO} , E_{HOMO} , J, Jhetv, BAC, IL	88	57.735	260.362	0.2217	0.7783	0.8495	0.8100	0.803

PRESS – Predicted residual sum of squares, SSY – sum of the squares of the response value, R^2_{CV} – overall predictive ability, S_{PRESS} – uncertainty of prediction, R^2_A – adjusted- R^2 , PSE – predictive square error.

cases r is much larger than 6PE indicating that all the proposed models have very good correlations.

Comments on R^2_A :

At this stage it will be very interesting to comment on R^2_A i.e. adjusted- R^2 , which takes into account the adjustment of R^2 . If variable is added that does not contribute its fair share, the R^2_A will actually decline. R^2 may appear artificially high if the number of variables is high compared to the sample size (i.e. the number of compound present in the computed model). Furthermore, R^2_A is a measure of the % explained variation in the dependent variable that takes into account the relationship between the number of cases and the number of independent variables in the regression model. Where as R^2 will always increase when an independent variable is added. R^2_A will decrease if the added variable doesn't reduce the unexplained variable enough to offset the loss of decrease of freedom.

In cases when we have used only topological indices for modeling log TA98 we obtained three statistically significant models expressed by eqs. (1)–(3). In all the three cases R^2_A goes on increasing and is highest for eq. (3). This means that the added independent variables have enough contribution to the proposed models. Also, that the optimum number of compounds for yielding the best model need to be 84 in place of 88. In case, when we have used log P along with the topological indices we obtained four statistically significant models expressed by eqs. (4)–(7). The R^2_A values for the eqs. (4) and (5) are the same; which means that the addition of E_{LUMO} doesn't have enough contribution to the model. When E_{HOMO} is used in place of E_{LUMO} , R^2_A increase to 0.806 from 0.815.

That indicates that the use of E_{HOMO} is much more favorable for the proposed model. When both E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} are added together there is decrease in the magnitude of R^2_A i.e. now it falls down from 0.815 to 0.813 clearly meaning that use of both these parameters (E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO}) together doesn't have their fair contributions. Finally, when we have used Balaban and Balaban type indices for modeling log TA98, we obtained six statistically significant models expressed by eqs. (9)–(14). The results show that except for eq. (13) the R^2_A goes on increasing as we pass from eqs. (9)–(14) and is the highest for eq. (14). A comparison of R^2_A value for eqs. (12) and (13) indicates that in this case contribution of E_{HOMO} is not favorable than the use of E_{LUMO} . However, when both (E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO}) parameters are used together, they contribute enough to the model ex-

Table 9. Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) for the proposed models

Model (eq.)	N	r	$1 - r^2$	PE	6PE
1 (1)	95	0.839	0.296	0.020	0.120
2 (2)	88	0.873	0.238	0.016	0.110
3 (3)	84	0.905	0.181	0.013	0.080
4 (4)	88	0.903	0.185	0.013	0.079
5 (5)	88	0.905	0.181	0.012	0.078
6 (6)	88	0.916	0.161	0.011	0.069
7 (7)	88	0.910	0.172	0.012	0.074
8 (8)	88	0.898	0.194	0.013	0.083
9 (9)	88	0.848	0.280	0.019	0.117
10 (10)	83	0.888	0.211	0.065	0.390
11 (11)	88	0.894	0.200	0.014	0.086
12 (12)	88	0.895	0.199	0.014	0.087
13 (13)	88	0.895	0.199	0.014	0.087
14 (14)	88	0.905	0.181	0.012	0.078

pressed by eq. (14).

Effect due to co-linearity :

From the results and discussion made above we observed that the models expressed by eqs. (3), (6) and (14) are best suited for modeling log TA98. It is, therefore, necessary to examine the existence of co-linearity defect, if any, in these models. If such defect exists then we will use the recommendation of Randic²⁷ for explaining it. However, at present the best way to examine such a defect is to obtain correlation matrix for the parameters involved in these models. Such correlation matrices obtained for eqs. (3), (6) and (14) are presented in Table 10. A perusal of this Table shows that ${}^2\chi$, ${}^2\chi^v$ and IL are linearly correlated in eq. (3); while in case of eqs. (6) and (14), the parameters log P and IL are linearly correlated. This means that all the three models suffer from the defect due to co-linearity. However, we can apply Randic recommendations²⁷ for explaining favorable recommendations for the use of these models for modeling log TA98.

According to him (Randic) under certain situations even highly correlated descriptors could be retained in the model. We will, therefore, use Randic's recommendations in the present case also. Randic stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression, such a descriptor in most studies should be discarded. For example ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^2\chi$, ${}^1\chi$ often strongly correlate and in many structure-property-activity studies ${}^2\chi$ has been discarded. This is not theoretically justified and the widespread practice should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure, it is important to recognize that even highly interrelated descrip-

Table 10. Correlation matrix for the inter-correlation of structural descriptors and their correlation with the activity

	log TA98	J	Jhetv	${}^2\chi$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^2\Delta$	IL	
log TA98	1.000							
J	-0.649	1.000						
Jhetv	-0.319	0.583	1.000					
${}^2\chi$	0.768	-0.709	-0.583	1.000				
${}^2\chi^v$	0.805	-0.787	-0.470	0.881	1.000			
${}^2\Delta$	0.465	-0.365	-0.461	0.812	0.460	1.000		
IL	0.764	-0.573	-0.391	0.579	0.634	0.340	1.000	
	log TA98	log P	E_{HOMO}	J	Jhetz	${}^1\Delta$	IL	
log TA98	1.000							
log P	0.723	1.000						
E_{HOMO}	0.338	0.031	1.000					
J	-0.604	-0.389	-0.534	1.000				
Jhetz	-0.548	-0.348	-0.524	0.920	1.000			
${}^1\Delta$	0.403	0.216	-0.053	-0.373	-0.389	1.000		
IL	0.771	0.464	0.403	-0.550	-0.570	0.248	1.000	
	log TA98	log P	E_{LUMO}	E_{HOMO}	J	Jhetv	BAC	IL
log TA98	1.000							
log P	0.723	1.000						
E_{LUMO}	-0.439	-0.361	1.000					
E_{HOMO}	0.338	0.031	0.370	1.000				
J	-0.604	-0.389	0.181	-0.534	1.000			
Jhetv	-0.277	-0.040	0.252	-0.165	0.595	1.000		
BAC	-0.248	-0.074	-0.059	-0.455	0.577	0.105	1.000	
IL	0.771	0.464	-0.369	0.403	-0.550	-0.363	-0.390	1.000

tors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small but nevertheless very important for structure-property relationship.

Optimum number of descriptors to be used : Rule of thumb :

Linear multiple regression is the technique that has been most used in quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR), which employs the least-squares method to find out the equation of “best-fit” of biological captivity with a given combination of correlating parameters. The limitation and some common pitfall of multiple regression analysis were pointed out by Tute^{28,29}. Accordingly, there must be a sufficient number of compounds included in the analysis to enable statistical significance to be reached, despite inevitable error in measurement. A rule of thumb was involved^{28,29} that at least five data point (compounds) should be included for every parameter and they themselves should be well “spread” and one must avoid the particular danger of including one extreme value of any parameter, as a “best-line” will inevitably pass through the extreme points. Looking to these requirements, we observed that all the 14 models proposed by us fulfill the requirement of rule of thumb^{28,29}.

However, this rule of thumb doesn't decide the optimum number of descriptors to be used in the proposed model. This, however, we can do by plotting a graph between the number of parameters used in the models against corresponding values of R^2 and R^2_A . Such a correlation as shown in Fig. 4 indicates that the optimum number of descriptors to be used is 6 to 7.

Conclusions :

From the results and discussion made above, we conclude that the present approach of using topological indices for modeling (log TA98) is better than the earlier methodology¹² in that quantum chemical parameters namely E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} were used. The present study also indicates that we can obtain models with considerably good statistics even without using the hydrophobic parameter viz. log P. However, use of log P along with topological indices resulted slight improvement in the statistics. Furthermore, our study show that use of Balaban and Balaban type indices for modeling the activity (log TA98) is quite good.

Experimental

(i) *Mutagenic activity (log TA98) :* The mutagenic ac-

Fig. 4. Correlation of R^2 and adjusted R^2 with number of descriptors used.

tivity namely log TA98 is the same as used in earlier paper¹².

(ii) *Quantum chemical parameters* : The calculated values of quantum chemical parameter : E_{LUMO} and E_{HOMO} are also adopted from earlier report¹².

(iii) *Topological indices* : All the topological indices were calculated from the hydrogen suppressed molecular graphs of aromatic and hetero-aromatic amines used. These indices are well documented in the literature¹⁴⁻¹⁹ and therefore, no details are given here. Except Szged index (Sz) all other topological indices were calculated using DRAGON software²¹ and the structure optimization is made using Hyperchem²² and ACD Labs²³ software. The calculation of Sz index is carried out using Luko-1 software of Lukovits.

(iv) *Regression analysis* : Molecular modeling is carried out regression analysis that the method of maximum- R^2 is adopted²⁰. The regression analysis is done using Regress-1 program of Lukovits (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, Hungary).

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